

E-RIHS

EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE
FOR HERITAGE SCIENCE

E-RIHS IP

European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science

IMPLEMENTATION Phase

CALL: HORIZON-INFRA-2021-DEV-02 | TYPE OF ACTION: CSA | GA n. 101079148

D5.3 E-RIHS ERIC Catalogue of Service: Approach and Advancement

**Authors: Laura Benassi, Jana Striova, Silvia Manconi, Diego Ivan
Quintero Balbas, Zita Szikszai**

Revisers: Brenda Doherty, Joseph Padfield, Sophia Sotiropoulou

ABSTRACT

Based on the experience of IPERION HS and other research infrastructures, the E-RIHS service catalogue will be built as a standalone platform and it will have two components: the frontend, that will have a user-friendly interface and the backend that will be composed of a system of dashboards and BI tools for monitoring the performance of the access provision over time.

The E-RIHS service catalogue will be implemented with a FAIR data management and in a way to be easily integrated and connected with the EOSC environment.

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Project number	101079148	Acronym	E-RIHS IP
Full title	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science Implementation Phase		
Project url	www.e-rihs.eu		
Document url			
EU Project Officer	Emiliano CAROZZA		

Deliverable	Number	D5.3	Title	E-RIHS ERIC Catalogue of Service: Approach and Advancement
Work Package	Number	5	Title	Access and Digital services of E-RIHS

Deliverable nature	Report		
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Confidential <input type="checkbox"/> Restricted		
Contractual delivery date	30/09/2023		
Actual delivery date	30/09/2023		
Status	Version 1.4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Final	

Authors (Partner)	National Research Council (CNR)	
Responsible Author	Name: Laura Benassi	Partner: CNR

Total number of pages	19
Keywords	Catalogue of Service, User, Facilities, DIGILAB, Digital

Version Log			
Issue Date	Rev. no.	Author	Change
04/09/2023	0.1	Laura Benassi, Jana Striova, Diego Quintero Balbas, Silvia Manconi, Zita Szikszai	First draft
18/09/2023	0.2	Brenda Doherty	Revision
19/09/2023	0.3	Sophia Sotiropoulou	Revision
20/09/2023	0.4	Joseph Padfield	Revision

DISCLAIMER: This document reflects only the author(s)'s view and the Agency and the European Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

1 TABLE OF CONTENTS

2	LIST OF FIGURES AND TABLES	5
3	ABBREVIATIONS.....	6
4	INTRODUCTION	7
4.1	APPROACH	7
4.1.1	<i>Status of the art</i>	<i>7</i>
4.2	THE EXPERIENCE OF OTHER RIS	8
4.2.1	<i>Mapping other Research Infrastructures</i>	<i>8</i>
5	ADVANCEMENT	9
5.1	TOWARDS THE DEFINITION OF THE E-RIHS SERVICES.....	9
5.2	THE FRONTEND OF THE E-RIHS SERVICE CATALOGUE	9
5.2.1	<i>Creation of a standalone portal and UX experience.....</i>	<i>9</i>
5.2.2	<i>Federated identity and authentication system</i>	<i>10</i>
5.2.3	<i>Application form.....</i>	<i>11</i>
5.3	THE BACKEND OF THE CATALOGUE	12
5.3.1	<i>The Dashboard system</i>	<i>12</i>
5.3.2	<i>Data Analytics tool.....</i>	<i>15</i>
5.4	A FAIR SERVICE CATALOGUE	16
6	CONCLUSION	17
7	REFERENCES.....	18

2 LIST OF FIGURES AND TABLES

Figure 1: the welcome page of the E-RIHS service catalogue 10
Figure 2: Screenshot of the appearance of the application form..... 12

3 ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviations	Expansion
ARCHLAB	Archives Laboratory
ARIADNE	Advance Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Data Networking in Europe
CERIC	Central European Research Infrastructure Consortium
CESSDA	Council of European Social Science Data Archives
CoS	Catalogue of Services
CSA	Cooperative and Support Action
DIGILAB	Digital Laboratory
DISSCO	Distributed System of Scientific Collections
ELIXIR	European Life-Science Infrastructure for Biological Information
ELVIS	European Loans and Visits System
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure on Heritage Science
EMBRC	European Marine Biology Resource Centre
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FIXLAB	Fixed Laboratories
HS	Heritage Science
iCNN	Interim Committee of National Nodes
iGA	Interim General Assembly
IPERION HS	Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure on Heritage Science
MLZ	Heinz Maier-Leibnitz Zentrum
MOLAB	Mobile Laboratories
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PARTHENOS	Polling Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage E-research networking, Optimization and Synergies
RIs	Research Infrastructure(s)
UH	User Helpdesk

4 INTRODUCTION

4.1 Approach

4.1.1 STATUS OF THE ART

A service catalogue of research infrastructure is a crucial tool to facilitate the access provision to communities of users and enable the discoverability of the services. In E-RIHS, services include techniques and tools, scientific archives, datasets, software, etc. and a solid expertise in the field of heritage science. Services are provided by facilities and laboratories of research organizations, museums and institutions across and beyond Europe.

A draft version of the catalogue of services of E-RIHS was developed inside the E-RIHS Preparatory Phase (Deliverable 8.1, available on [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org/record/4002040)) in 2020 and experimented with in IPERION HS (starting from 2020: <https://www.iperionhs.eu/catalogue/>). Based on the experience and data gained in previous projects (such as IPERION CH, ARIADNE, and PARTHENOS), and after the first recognition of the resources, a conceptual model was created and implemented as a Relational Database Management System. The challenge was to organize the heterogeneity of data and metadata of a multidisciplinary community without the support of consolidated ontologies and taxonomies. Anyway, specific entities were created to cover the broad categories of information (service, provider, contact person, technique, tools, archive, platform, etc.)¹ and some controlled lists of metadata were created in a collaborative way with the providers.

IPERION HS services are divided into three platforms: ARCHLAB, FIXLAB, and MOLAB, each led by a coordinator. Each platform has a specific characteristic and requires different approaches. Taking into account the complexity of IPERION HS services, the service catalogue is currently organized as an e-commerce catalogue to minimize the efforts of the users, already familiar with the system used by the main e-commerce companies (e.g., Amazon).

The catalogue includes two ways for users to access it: one is guided and dedicated to non-expert users, and the other one is through a dynamic architecture and search engine for users who have already experimented with the services of the community in previous projects or for skilled users.

Users must log in, browse techniques and tools, add one or more to the cart, and complete an application form in order to submit a proposal. Once submitted, it must first pass the technical feasibility and after the scientific review of an international panel of experts.

To facilitate access management, a system of dashboard has been created with different levels of permission (platform coordinator, user helpdesk, provider, and user). The platform coordinator and the user helpdesk can overview all the applications and take appropriate action as needed. An automatic system of emails sends information to all the subjects involved in a specific application during the different steps of the evaluation (submitted, feasible, non-feasible, partially feasible, reviewed, etc...) and the access provision. The last thing to do is up to the user, who must participate in two surveys and upload a report (called “post-access duties”).

¹ For a detailed description of the Conceptual data model developed in E-RIHS PP and experimented in IPERION HS, read the deliverable 8.1 available in Zenodo: <https://www.zenodo.org/record/4002040> (2020)

All the data and files can be downloaded and analysed to monitor the access performance of IPERION HS providers.

Progress on the implementation of the catalogue was marked by several key achievements. First, UX testing was carried out to fix bugs and unclear submission processes. Second, existing solutions have been analysed to identify the best approach for ensuring a user-friendly experience for the users. In the heritage science community, users of the E-RIHS services are mostly Cultural Heritage professionals, such as curators and scientists, scholars, and students.

In the last three years, users and providers tested the IPERION HS catalogue and the team in charge of the catalogue collected all the criticalities for future budget-related improvements. One of the relevant upgrades will be the dashboard of the reviewers to allow them to evaluate the applications directly in the system.

In the meantime, new catalogues of services and marketplaces were developed by other research infrastructures and clouds.

4.2 The experience of other RIs

4.2.1 MAPPING OTHER RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

Comparing the IPERION HS catalogue with others’ service catalogues is a time-saving approach to improving it in view of the E-RIHS ERIC catalogue.

Two methods were used to map the existing solutions: conducting direct interviews with the managers of the research infrastructures and experimenting with the others’ catalogue as a user.

The analysed catalogues are:

Catalogues		
ELIXIR	Health and food	https://elixir-europe.org/services
EMBRC ERIC	Health and food	https://www.embrc.eu/service-catalogue
CESSDA ERIC	Social and cultural Innovation	https://www.cessda.eu/Tools
CERIC ERIC	Physical Sciences and Engineering	https://vuo.elettra.eu/pls/vuo/guest.startup
MLZ	Physical Sciences and Engineering	https://gneus.eu/mlz/
DISSCO	Environment	https://elvis.dissco.eu/welcome
Marketplaces		
SSHOC	Social and Cultural Innovation	https://sshoc-marketplace.acdh-dev.oeaw.ac.at/
EOSC	Data, Computing and Digital research	https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/

We included the marketplaces in the list even if “marketplace” differs structurally from a “service catalogue”.

As a result, mostly three case studies offered inspiring solutions : the Virtual Unified Office of CERIC ERIC (<https://vuo.elettra.eu/>), the GNeuS Portal of MLZ (<https://gneus.eu/mlz/>), and the ELVIS portal of DISSCO (<https://elvis.dissco.eu/welcome>). These products are used with different objectives with respect to the E-RIHS situation and from different types of communities. Anyway, each of them has some specific, interesting features applicable to the new E-RIHS catalogue.

The interviews allowed for a clear understanding of the workflow behind the catalogue and of the management of the evaluation process. The description of the structure and mechanism of the reviewers' dashboard was invaluable.

5 ADVANCEMENT

5.1 Towards the definition of the E-RIHS services

In line with the “D5.5 E-RIHS ERIC Access Policy: Approach and Advancement” document, access refers to the legitimated and authorised physical, remote, and virtual admission to the interaction with E-RIHS services offered. Such access is granted, amongst others, to machine time, computing resources, software, data, communication services data, sample preparation, archives, collections, the set-up, execution, and dismantling of experiments, expert support, and analytical services. Thus, the term service refers to activities that are offered to a wider community and initiated by Users, distinguishing them from joint research or other types of activities. E-RIHS services will comprise offers that are currently available within IPERION HS, as well as new types of possibilities. They are a dynamic set of items, updated according to User needs and availability at the national nodes.

5.2 The frontend of the E-RIHS service catalogue

5.2.1 CREATION OF A STANDALONE PORTAL AND UX EXPERIENCE

The E-RIHS service catalogue will be created as an independent platform, based on a scalable and modular architecture, which can be easily adapted and expanded to meet future needs and integrate new functionalities. The will be created to host the E-RIHS service catalogue, the dashboards and all the information necessary to apply and carry out access. The decision is driven by the need to freely customize the structure of the catalogue and improve the usability of the dashboard and the service catalogue.

The service catalogue will be composed of a frontend and a backend (a system of dashboards).

The frontend will be built with a user-friendly interface and will propose different ways to browse the services:

1. Through the ElasticSearch engine that combines semantic search with artificial intelligence and allows fast search, fine-tuned relevancy, and powerful analytics that scale with ease.
2. Through a sort of matrix that will allows users to automatically match “research needs” with the “relevant techniques”.
3. Through a dynamic system of filters.

The service catalogue will be pass through usability tests to fix bug and improve the users' experience. It will be defined the test objectives, the user profile, the questions, the scenario, and

the tasks and inputs, assumptions, and steps will be collected to validate the new E-RIHS catalogue of services in all its components: description of the services, registration form, application form and the dashboard. An improved version of the portal will be released after each UX test.

The frontend will be the showcase of the E-RIHS access offer. It will be structured as an ecommerce website where the user can find one or more services and put them into a cart. Once defined the request/s, the user will have to fill in the personal profile and submit a proposal through an application form. The proposal will be evaluated from the providers (about feasibility) and from a Peer Review Panel of international experts who will rank the proposal according to defined criteria.

The consortium is building a new approach: from a “technique-oriented catalogue” to a “research need-oriented catalogue”. A working group is collecting and listing possible research needs to use for this scope, another one is defining controlled lists and vocabularies to use in the description of the service (<https://github.com/E-RIHS>). Each service will be illustrated with technical descriptions, bibliographical references, videos, etc.

Materials on the use of the catalogue and dashboards will be produced and uploaded to the portal; specific courses will be organized to train providers and users on the same topic.

Figure 1: The welcome page of the E-RIHS service catalogue

5.2.2 FEDERATED IDENTITY AND AUTHENTICATION SYSTEM

The service catalogue can be browsed by logging in. For the moment, E-RIHS has chosen to use consolidated and secure single sign-on standards and not to create its own federated identity. The

authentication system will enable users to securely authenticate with multiple software systems by using just one set of credentials.

Users can sign up (and after sign in) by:

1. creating a basic E-RIHS account (email, password, confirmation of the password, Recaptha), accepting the terms and conditions, and activating the account
2. using ORCID, the persistent identifier which stands for Open Researcher and Contributor ID. E-RIHS is an ESFRI research infrastructure and ESFRI supports Open Science. The use of ORCID is in line with an open access policy.

At the beginning, users are registered as a simple “user”. The UH is emailed upon any new registration. In cases where the person has a role different from the simple user, the UH changes the role to “reviewer” or “provider”. The reviewer and the provider can be concurrently simple users and submit applications. In this case, they will have two separate dashboards to manage the different roles.

Because ORCID doesn’t release some information, in a homogeneous way, it was necessary to create a “detailed personal profile” for users who want to submit a proposal. Previous application forms included specific information required by the European Commission for statistical purposes. In the new application form, users are required to fill out the same fields, such as country, nationality, birth year, position, etc., for the same reasons.

When filled out, users can access the personal dashboard where they can find the detailed personal profile, the documents (images, reports, etc.), the list of the applications submitted, under evaluation, not granted, archived, etc.

5.2.3 APPLICATION FORM

Discussion on the application form is ongoing. The basis is the IPERION HS application form, but the new version is organized differently and has a few fields that will be used to feed the algorithm that will be developed to match applications with the reviewers.

The consortium and the iCNN will validate the application form over the coming months. It will be organized into the following sections:

1. Services summary – where users can check the required tools, add or remove tools after the assessment of the feasibility
2. Proposal and workplan – here users describe the scientific proposals and insert the specifications of the object to analyse
3. The team – the user group leader must include information about scientific background and can add other users to the team
4. Additional information – here users can link the applications to other EU projects or proposals
5. Terms and conditions – users must agree with the access policy and the post-access duties.

Users can check the application history and verify the status of the proposal step by step by using the dashboard system, described below (chapter 5.2.1).

Figure 2: Screenshot of the appearance of the application form

5.3 The backend of the catalogue

5.3.1 THE DASHBOARD SYSTEM

The dashboard is a data management system that collects and organizes data, and it is set up in line with a precise workflow.

The E-RIHS system of dashboards is a tool with different levels of permission for different roles to access and manage the information from the backend of the service catalogue. There are four types of roles:

1. User
2. Access Provider
3. Reviewer
4. User Helpdesk (UH) / Access Coordinator

Compared to the IPERION HS dashboards organized in a single table, the new dashboards will be structured with a system of tabs to browse different parts where all the components are stored (eg. List of applications, List of Documents, Application history, etc.). This way, all materials will be available clearly and easily.

Users can complete the personal profile, browse resources, write and submit a proposal, save draft, change tools before the submission or after the first step of evaluation, upload files (report, photo,

etc.). Users can also add other users to the team. The team members can only visualize the application. The User Group Leader can authorize one team member to manage the application on behalf of her/him. Users have access to a personal dashboard (a webpage) where to view the list of all their applications and the granted applications and check the status of the application submitted.

The Provider can assess the feasibility of the proposals, comments, and ticks that the access has been carried out at the facility.

The Reviewer can fill out the profile with competencies and declarations (No conflict of interest, etc...), evaluate the proposals assigned, make comments separately for the user and for the User Helpdesk.

The User Helpdesk (UH) and the Access Coordinator can overview all the proposals, change the status of the proposals, manage the algorithm for the choice of the reviewers, archive proposals.

Thanks to the dashboards, it is possible to follow the status of a proposal that changes over time depending on the actions carried out:

draft – saved – submitted – feasible/unfeasible/partially feasible – under review – main list – below threshold – reserve list – access scheduled – carried out – close – archived

A system of alerts (green, yellow, red, and blue traffic lights) encourages the owners of the dashboards to take action when needed. Green means "Everything goes well" – no action is needed: the whole proposal is feasible and can be sent to the reviewers for evaluation. If the proposal is granted, the facility/ies can arrange access with the User Group Leader. Yellow means "You have to do/check something": the (multi-service) proposal is partially feasible. Red means "Something has gone wrong" - a proposal is not feasible: what to do? Blue means that the access has been carried out and the proposal is archived.

5.3.1.1 DEFINING THE ACCESS WORKFLOW

The workflow of the service catalogue can have a strong impact on other activities and strategies of the research infrastructure. When defining the workflow, it is necessary to consider the Access Policy and intervene in the communication strategy.

For the new E-RIHS service catalogue, the consortium is still discussing some elements that could take different directions depending on the final approval of the iGA and iCNN.

The consortium considered two different possibilities for providing access:

1. a workflow where applications can be submitted on a continuous basis, passed through the feasibility and immediately peer reviewed, without any cut off deadline
2. a workflow with periodic cut-off deadlines.

In the end, the decision was to use the workflow with cut-off deadlines. The calls allow a competitive ranking of proposals and guarantee to maintain high-level standards in line with awarding access for scientific excellence.

The workflow with cut off deadlines can be described as follows:

When users submit an application, they need to fill out the profile in detail with information. Users insert the proposal by using the **online application form**.

Once submitted, the application receives the “**submitted**” status. An email is sent to the UH and the user about the successful submission of the application.

When the application status is “submitted”, an automatic email is sent to the provider/s involved to inform them about the submission of an application and request for a first assessment of feasibility starting thirty days before the cut-off deadline. The application can be feasible, partially feasible or unfeasible.

If the proposal is **“feasible”**, at the deadline, the provider confirms the feasibility. An email will be sent to the user to confirm the final submission of the proposal and its feasibility, and the application passes for review. The system chooses three reviewers, and an automatic email informs the user, the UH and the provider/s.

If the proposal is **“partially feasible”** or **“unfeasible”**, the application comes back to the status of a draft. An email is sent to the UH that the proposal is not feasible or partially feasible. An email is sent to the user to inform about the unfeasibility or partial feasibility and suggests contacting the UH. The user contacts the UH and can decide whether to change tool/s or remove criticalities and resubmit the proposal or not.

If the proposal is resubmitted, it passes through a second step of feasibility. This process can be done only twice.

If the proposal becomes feasible, at the deadline, the provider confirms the new feasibility. An email is sent to the user to confirm the final submission of the proposal and its feasibility, and the application passes for review.

At the **cut-off deadline**, the system chooses three reviewers. The UH confirms or modifies the selection of the reviewers and clicks on **“confirm the reviewers”**. An automatic email is sent to the reviewers to inform them that they have been selected for a specific application with the following information:

ID application | Title of the proposal | Project summary | User

At this point, each reviewer checks the conflicts of interest for this specific application **within seven days**.

If the reviewer checks the conflict of interests within seven days and is not in conflict of interests, the reviewer is qualified to evaluate the application.

If the reviewer doesn't check the conflict by the end of seven days, an email is sent to the reviewer and the UH to solicit the reviewer and check it in the **next three days**. The system will allow the reviewer to check it in the next 3 days.

If the reviewer still does not respond, an automatic email notifies the reviewer that the process has ended for him/her/them and the UH will select another reviewer.

If the reviewer checks the conflict in the next three days and is not in a conflict of interest, the reviewer is qualified to evaluate.

If the reviewer checks the conflict of interests in seven days and is in conflict of interests, an email informs the reviewer that the process ends for her/him/them and the UH to select another reviewer.

When all three reviewers have declared no conflict of interest, the evaluation starts and the status of the proposal changes to **“under review”**. The reviewers will have three-four weeks to evaluate the assigned proposals.

If everything is okay, the reviewer must score the application based on defined criteria.

When a reviewer ends the evaluation, he/she/they press the “**evaluation made**” button. The system sends an email to the UH stating that the reviewer has scored the application.

If two reviewers provided a homogeneous evaluation, the UH can decide to go ahead when two of the three reviewers have evaluated the application and press the “**stop the evaluation**” button. The UH verifies the score. Depending on the score, the UH changes the status of the application to “**Main List**”, “**Reserve List**” or “**Below Threshold**”.

If the application is below the threshold, an email informs the provider/s that the application didn’t pass the review. Another email is sent to the user to inform him/her/them of the decision and invite he/she/them to contact the UH for a potential resubmission.

If the application is on the main list, an email is sent to inform the user and the provider and invite them to schedule access.

If the application is on the reserve list, it can be recovered at any time or resubmitted to a new call. An email is sent to the user and suggest contacting the UH before a new submission.

If the user hasn’t contacted the provider in **fifteen days**, an email is sent to the UH to solicit the provider.

When the provider contacts the user, the provider clicks on “**access scheduled**” and organizes the access with the user.

When the access is carried out, the provider/s changes the status of the proposal to “**carried out**” (with the date).

If the application is for multi-facilities, when all the providers have clicked on “carried out”, the system changes the status of the application to “**closed**” and an email is sent to the user, the provider/s and the UH to inform them that the access has been carried out and ask the user for surveys and **post-access report**.

An automatic email is sent periodically for two months to the user to require the post access duties.

When the user submits the post-access duties, in two months, as required, the system changes the status of the application to **archived**. An automatic email is sent to the user, the provider, and the UH to inform them that the process is successfully closed.

If the user doesn’t submit the post-access duties by two months, the process ends for the user, and the system doesn’t allow the user to submit another application for the next 12 months or until the user upload the report.

The consortium is still discussing the number of calls per year and is evaluating the possibility of introducing fast-track calls for the ARCHLAB platform or for proposals asking for only one provider.

5.3.2 DATA ANALYTICS TOOL

At each call, IPERION HS received many applications with a huge amount of data and files to analyse. Thanks to a plugin, in IPERION HS it was possible to download all the applications and their attachments extracting some details (e.g. id, title, platform, description of the project, keywords, disciplines, etc.) in a excel format.

For the E-RIHS service catalogue, a more advanced tool of business intelligence will be used to extrapolate data accordingly with the KPIs, defined inside the WP 3. Data can be explored, filtered, aggregated, and visualized in real time for monitoring the access performances:

- Number of submitted proposals
- Nationality of the User Group Leader
- Gender
- Community of belonging of user
- Number of users participating in the proposal
- Type of proposal (new, continuation, resubmission)
- Access to a platform (ARCHLAB, DIGILAB, FIXLAB, MOLAB)
- Scientific disciplines of user and research proposal
- Tools requested
- Providers requested
- Research needs
- Number of proposals granted
- Number of proposals rejected
- Number of proposals carried out
- Status of proposal
- ...

This information will be useful to periodically evaluate the access and communication strategy and consider the trends of the research infrastructure in terms of sustainability and performance.

5.4 A FAIR service catalogue

A strategy is being studied to make the E-RIHS service catalogue FAIR. ESFRI supports Open Science and asks the research infrastructures to act as the “main promoters of Open Science providing FAIR and quality certified Open Data”². Research infrastructures should contribute to the EOSC environment, “leading the change of culture, driving data quality and more open access to data”. Following this premise, the E-RIHS service catalogue will be implemented to make EOSC able to easily harvest and integrate data and research outputs.

This connection is fundamental because research infrastructures are on one side providers of data and services, and on the other side users of services provided by EOSC.

The E-RIHS service catalogue will be integrated with information and tools to help users practising open science. Some conditions included in the terms according to access modality will oblige users to draft a data management plan and release datasets and reports in open access with an embargo on the pending publications of the results.

Users will be guided to attribute the proper Creative Commons licenses to each type of research outputs and to disseminate the research results.

² Making science happen. ESFRI white paper, available at: <https://www.esfri.eu/esfri-white-paper> (2020)

6 CONCLUSION

Based on the experience of the IPERION HS and on the service catalogues of other research infrastructures, the E-RIHS catalogue represents the single-entry point for the E-RIHS services. The construction of this catalogue is the result of a long-term, interdisciplinary collaboration inside the consortium. E-RIHS is a complex community and convergence towards this tool has required many efforts across multiple disciplines. Some features can only be consolidated using the catalogue.

The service catalogue is currently being built as a flexible system capable of integrating future needs and applications. When the service catalogue will be sufficiently implemented with all the information, a recommendation system associated with machine learning will be developed to give every user a personalized experience. The system will suggest or recommend additional services on the basis of the behavior of other users who have already requested some services for the same research need. At the beginning, the system will be trained to understand the preferences and decisions, and then it will be able to drive users towards appropriate choices.

The application of artificial intelligence represents an added value to the catalogue and offers a facilitation to obtain services, but also considering the co-creation of knowledge strategy supported by the European Commission, it is obvious that the best way to help advancement and innovation in research is building strong (human) relationships between the research infrastructure and its users.

7 REFERENCES

D8.1 Catalogue of E-RIHS resources and services, Meghini C., Benassi L., Galeotti M, et al., DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4002040, available on Zenodo/E-RIHS community, <https://www.zenodo.org/record/4002040>

<https://elvis.dissco.eu/welcome>

<https://www.ceric-eric.eu/users/login-to-vuo/>

<https://github.com/E-RIHS>

<https://gneus.eu/mlz/>

<https://elixir-europe.org/services>

<https://www.embrc.eu/service-catalogue>

<https://www.cessda.eu/Tools>